

Yield, spikelet fertility, and days to maturity of hybrids using 12 restorer lines.^a Punjab, India.

Male parent	Grain yield (g)/10 plants			Male parent selfed	Spikelet fertility (%)			Male parent selfed	Days to maturity			Male parent	
	Hybrid combination with				Hybrid combination with				Hybrid combination with				
	V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		V20A	IR46830A	IR48483A		
PAU50-B-25-1-5	420.33	138.67	102.00	280.00	82.53	59.93	41.82	88.85	128	130	138	143	
PAU158-68-1-1	340.00	123.67	72.67	229.00	83.96	60.94	43.63	88.26	123	123	123	133	
PAU164-11-3-4-1	334.67	309.33	268.33	259.00	78.15	76.69	75.93	87.12	140	133	138	141	
IR18341-37-3-2	324.67	148.00	111.33	247.00	91.35	75.15	57.65	84.48	135	138	138	138	
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	296.00	195.67	158.00	235.67	80.47	68.89	49.24	85.74	138	136	137	140	
IR28178-82-31	334.33	209.67	166.00	222.67	83.02	72.15	60.77	89.01	133	126	129	138	
MRC603-3-3	366.67	85.33	45.33	226.33	79.26	60.63	34.48	80.05	126	124	121	123	
BR51-282-7	278.33	155.67	128.67	271.33	85.55	73.21	75.29	87.21	128	126	126	141	
UPR82-1-1	367.33	135.33	94.67	248.00	87.59	71.95	65.93	87.88	118	122	120	115	
Palman 579	194.00	76.67	52.00	229.00	72.25	46.66	34.32	89.15	123	128	128	126	
PR103	427.67	300.33	255.33	368.33	83.20	75.60	72.39	88.46	120	123	122	125	
PR106	328.00	245.33	155.00	416.67	82.66	72.64	52.08	84.96	128	132	131	144	
LSD													
		Grain yield		Spikelet fertility									
		0.05-13.078		0.05-1.115									
		0.01-17.142		0.01-2.866									

^aPR106 = best check.

Effect of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) on panicle exertion and sheath rot (ShR) incidence in F₂ rice hybrids

K.K. Vinod, P. Vivekanandan, and M. Subramanian, Genetics and Plant Breeding Division, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the F₂ progenies of indica rice hybrids Zhen Shan 97A/IR50, Er-jiu-nan 1A/IR50, and MS37A/IR50 carrying wild abortive CMS in 1988 wet season. Segregants were examined for pollen and spikelet fertility, panicle exertion, and ShR incidence.

All crosses segregated for fertile, partially fertile, and sterile classes on the basis of pollen and spikelet fertility (see table). Panicle exertion was invariably poor in all the sterile and

near sterile plants in all crosses. All plants with well-exserted or moderately well-exserted panicles were completely fertile.

ShR incidence was severe in plants with poorly exerted panicles. The higher ShR incidence in sterile plants

was attributed to half-opened leaf sheaths covering the lower half of the panicles: that favored infection.

We conclude that panicle exertion might be under the influence of cytoplasmic-genetic factors that control CMS in rice. □

Effect of CMS on panicle exertion, fertility, and ShR incidence in the F₂ of hybrid rices. Madurai, India, 1988.

Hybrid	Panicle exertion	Spikelet fertility (%)	Pollen fertility (%)	ShR incidence ^a
Zhen Shan 97A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 33.7	0.0 - 30.0	7
	Just exerted	40.3 - 96.8	30.0 - 100.0	5
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1
Er-jiu-nan 1A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 28.2	0.0 - 30.0	7
	Just exerted	41.0 - 98.3	30.0 - 100.0	3
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1
MS37A/IR50	Partly exerted	0.0 - 43.8	0.0 - 30.0	7-9
	Just exerted	60.1 - 100.0	30.0 - 100.0	5
	Moderately well- or well-exserted	>90.0	90.0 - 100.0	1

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Identification of restorers and maintainers for male sterile lines at CLRRI

Pham Cong Voc, Pham Thi Mui, and Nguyen Van Luat, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI), Omon, Haugiang Vietnam

We testcrossed 22 short- and medium-duration rice cultivars with cytoplasmic male sterile lines IR46829A, IR46830A, IR48483A, and IR54752A, than 10% fertility as suspected maintainers.

OM576, OM80, IR66, and IR29723-143-3-2-2-2-1 were identified as

effective restorers for IR46830A and IR54752A (see table). OM86-9, OM90, and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 were effective restorers for IR48483A. to identify fertility restorers and sterility maintainers.

Hybrids and their male parents were transplanted in 1987-88 dry and wet